

Context over convenience: a critical perspective on spatial weights in applied spatial research

Fillipe Oliveira Feitosa^{1,2,*}, René Westerholt¹

1: Department of Spatial Planning, TU Dortmund University, Germany

2: Institute for Geoinformatics, University of Münster, Germany

* Correspondence: Fillipe Oliveira Feitosa, Institute for Geoinformatics, University of Münster, Heisenbergstr. 2, 48149 Münster, Germany. Email: fillipe.feitosa@uni-muenster.de

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Abstract:

In spatial analysis, the use of geometric distance and physical adjacency as the basis for spatial weights matrices (SWMs) has long been a quasi-standard. These methods offer clarity and computational convenience, yet they often oversimplify how spatial relationships actually function. Many spatial processes are shaped by more than just physical proximity, making conventional SWMs insufficient in certain contexts. This work critically examines the over-reliance on traditional spatial weights and introduces a structured approach for recognising cases where alternative models should be considered.

We highlight a range of contexts where spatial dependence defies the logic of simple distance or adjacency. These include settings shaped by institutional connections, digital systems, economic interactions, and other non-physical networks. In such cases, dependencies may be unequal, evolve over time, or emerge from feedback mechanisms and spillover effects. Applying standard, off-the-shelf SWMs in these contexts can lead to misleading interpretations, masking the actual forces shaping spatial dynamics, and weakening the credibility of empirical findings.

Rather than endorsing a universal technical fix, we advocate for a modelling approach grounded in the specific features of the spatial phenomena under investigation. Our main argument extends beyond methods, fostering a conceptual and critical analysis. Spatial structures should emerge from the actual relationships and mechanisms present in phenomena, not be imposed through predetermined geometric assumptions.

The goal is to encourage a paradigm shift from defaulting to proximity-based models toward more nuanced, theory-informed modelling practices. This involves critically assessing when traditional SWMs suffice and when they might fail. By doing so, researchers can build spatial models that are not only methodologically sound but can better reflect the lived and (possibly) relational geographies.

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